

**DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF AN ECO-FRIENDLY
HYDROELECTRIC POWER GENERATION AND STORAGE
SYSTEM FOR ENERGY CONSERVATION IN
SUSTAINABLE SOCIETIES.**

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this project on “Design And Development Of An Eco-Friendly Hydroelectric Power Generation And Storage System For Energy Conservation In Sustainable Societies” is an undergraduate research work carried out and written by **THOMAS, OLUWAFEMI JOHNSON** under the supervision of PROFESSOR A.F. ADISA, Department of Agricultural and Bioresources Engineering, College of Engineering, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta.

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CERTIFICATION

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DEDICATION

This research is dedicated to Almighty God for granting me the grace, strength, and guidance throughout the duration of this project and my entire program. I also extend my heartfelt gratitude to my loving and always supportive family for their unwavering moral and financial support throughout every phase of my life, especially in helping me complete my undergraduate studies.

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ABSTRACT

This project addresses the critical challenges of energy generation in Nigeria, a country with a significant yet underutilised potential for renewable energy, particularly in the context of mini hydroelectric power generation. The project is described as an innovative approach to energy generation, aiming to design and fabricate a mini hydroelectric power generator capable of producing and storing electricity efficiently. This generator is designed to operate as a power generation and storage system, as it utilises a self-adjusting system that redirects water used to turn the turbine to a storage tank, enabling energy conservation during periods of low consumption.

This study investigates the potential of a small-scale hydroelectric power generation and storage system in sustainable urban environments. The system's performance was evaluated by varying the opening angles of the outlet valves in two water reservoirs. The overhead reservoir generated a maximum of 10.36 watts at a fully opened valve (90° angle), while the storage reservoir produced up to 5.73 watts under the same conditions. After accounting for the energy expended in pumping water back to the storage reservoir, the system achieved a net power savings of approximately 9.09 watts. This surplus energy can be utilised during peak demand periods, such as winter or low wind conditions.

The findings indicate that small-scale hydroelectric systems can significantly enhance urban energy efficiency by storing excess energy generated during low-demand periods and providing a reliable power supply during high-demand times. This approach not only improves energy management but also contributes to the overall sustainability of cities by reducing dependency on non-renewable energy sources. However, the study's limitations, including its controlled experimental conditions and the need for integration with other renewable energy sources, suggest areas for further research to optimise the system's performance in real-world applications.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0. Introduction

The world's energy demand is on the rise, accompanied by a rapid increase in population, resulting in a large amount spent on the importation of oil (Augustine Takase *et al.*, 2021; Diyoke *et al.*, 2022; Ramarope *et al.*, 2023). It is without dispute that oil and electricity are the primary factors that determine economic growth and has impact on all developing aspects such as environment, society, economy, agriculture, population and livelihood (Augustine Takase *et al.*, 2021). Developing countries in Africa face different economic and sociopolitical challenges thus, severely affecting the development of the power sector (Elabbas *et al.*, 2023). According to Augustine Takase *et al.* (2022), about 2 billion people have no access to electricity, and the increase in population, particularly in developing countries, would lead to an increase in energy demand in the world. Analysis from Elabbas *et al.* (2023) concludes that Africa, home to about 17% of the world's population, has about 5% access rate of electricity, which complements the research made by Augustine Takase *et al.* (2022), and to completely meet the power needs and to build the necessary infrastructure, an estimate of 20 billion dollars is required.

Nevertheless, the increasing need for power, or in this case electricity, is being met through the use of fossil fuels or traditional resources such as coal, natural gas, and oil, which make up about 80% of total electricity production (Amir, 2022; Agoundedemba *et al.*, 2023). Combined with this is the alarming rate of increase in climate change and its impact. Nonetheless, ensuring adequate, affordable, and reliable sources with lessened carbon footprint is very vital for a lot of countries in Africa that are struggling to achieve their daily demand of energy (Augustine Takase *et al.*, 2021).

Figure 1: Electrification access rate in some African countries (%)

Source: Agoundedemba *et al.* (2023)

Figure 1 above shows the electrification assessment rate in some African countries, Nigeria inclusive. The chart shows that there is a power assessment rate of less than 50% in Nigeria of which the majority depends on fossil fuels and will eventually make fossil fuels an insufficient source of energy for the future due to sophisticated technological development (Ihobhebhe *et al.*, 2023). It is crucial to acknowledge that Nigeria possesses abundant sources of both fossil fuels and renewable energy. However, a significant obstacle lies in the inefficient utilization of these resources (Samuel and Oladimeji, 2020). Despite the country's substantial energy potential, much of it remains untapped, contributing to ongoing challenges in the energy sector, particularly in the inadequate generation of electricity (Adebanji *et al.*, 2023).

1.1. Problem Statement

1.1.1. Power Generation Landscape in Nigeria

Data obtained from International Trade Administration (2023), concludes that Nigeria has a thermal and hydropower generation capacity of 12,522 MW. However, energy production data from March 2005 to July 2023 has shown an average of only 3,970.33 MW, which is about 32% of total usage. This is due to certain factors as highlighted by Emovon *et al.* (2017).

1.1.2. Power Generation Problems and Challenges in Nigeria

According to research made by Emovon *et al.* (2017) and Emovon and Samuel (2017), the major challenges facing power generation in Nigeria are Lack or mixed energy (being over-dependent on one or two sources of energy and not the mix of other sources of energy), improper maintenance, corruption, inadequate funding to purchase modern equipment and maintain existing infrastructure, militant activities such as pipeline vandalism, inadequate manpower for operating and maintenance of equipment, siting of power plants in wrong location, and lack of policy continuity. When there is inconsistency in policies related to power generation over time, it can create uncertainties and hinder the development of a stable and efficient energy sector.

1.1.3. Renewable Energy Integration

The discovery of fossil fuels has significantly advanced human societies. However, the rapid depletion and environmental drawbacks of fossil resources are concerns (Samuel and Oladimeji, 2020). As emphasizes by Onwumelu (2023), humanity has consistently devised ways to generate and utilize energy for diverse purposes within their communities throughout history. Going back to ancient times, wood, categorized as biomass, has been employed for various functions like cooking, heating, and lighting (Sa'ad and Bugaje, 2016). Technological progress eventually led to the adoption of hydro energy for power generation through

hydropower turbines. However, according to the bar chart produced by Molua *et al.* (2023), hydropower production has always been on the low but on the good side, has a low rate of emission.

Figure 2: Comparative Analysis of Energy Generation Cost and Emission Intensity.

Source: Molua *et al.* (2023)

Solar energy has the potential to generate approximately 1850×10^3 GWh of solar electricity annually if just 1% of Nigeria's land mass is covered with solar modules (Adeyemi-Kayode *et al.*, 2021). This capacity for power generation exceeds current production by more than 100 times, but, as outlined by Emovon and Samuel (2017), practical implementation faces challenges. While solar energy has gained popularity recently, it does have drawbacks, such as storage issues and limited sunlight duration. In Nigeria, hydroelectric power remains the most utilized option (Adeyemi-Kayode *et al.*, 2021). Nevertheless, there is a consistent decline in hydroelectric power generation, and the utilization of natural gas, oil, and coal sources is not keeping pace with population growth (Bala *et al.*, 2020). According to Adeyemi-Kayode *et al.* (2021), Dodo *et al.* (2021), and Ramarope *et al.* (2023), small hydropower sources have not

received adequate research attention and remain underdeveloped in Nigeria. These energy generation sources are very important not just to generate energy, but to capture carbon in the atmosphere CO₂ (a greenhouse gas) due to the combustion of fossil fuels and to mitigate its contribution to global warming. In addition, upon a high energy value generation potential, there is under utilisation of the amount of energy generated, leading to wastage of the excessively produced energy.

1.2. Project Description

The project aims to address a variety of power generation challenges by introducing a mini hydroelectric power generator that can be used for energy conservation and storage. The intended users of this innovative solution are sustainable cities and areas where there are natural sources of water and potential for utilisation. The mini hydroelectric power generator will be assembled from several components, including overhead semi-circular reservoirs placed at different heights, a metal pipe frame, an outlet valve, a power generator, a water wheel, water transfer hoses, and a water pump.

Distinguishing itself from other power generation initiatives, this project presents a unique feature. Unlike solar power systems dependent on sunlight availability, the mini hydroelectric generator will be able to produce electricity and store energy in the form of potential energy as well as kinetic energy. Achieving this sustainability initiative involves utilizing a self-adjusting system (a pump) to redirect the volume of water used to turn the turbine to a tank at a position below the overhead tank for storage when the consumption of energy is minimal in society (at night) or at peak energy generation and will be reused when there is insufficient energy production capability, in winter or periods of drought. Moreover, the project addresses the common shortcomings of many portable hydroelectric turbines by incorporating an electricity storage device, and a battery, ensuring that the system can store generated electricity for future use when immediate consumption is unnecessary.

1.3. Objectives of the Project

1.3.1. General Objectives

Development of a Mini Hydroelectric power generator.

1.3.2. Specific Objectives

1. To design and fabricate a Mini Hydroelectric power generator.
2. Determining voltage output on varying discharge from the collective storage tanks.
3. Evaluating the efficiency of power production and storage of the mini hydroelectric generator.
4. Initiating a continuous development topic for researchers into implementing storage systems in mini hydroelectric plants.

1.4. Justification

It is important to carry out this project because it contributes significantly to economic and environmental sustainability by harnessing clean and renewable energy from nature (SDG 7: Clean and Affordable Energy). The project also fosters more research into the use of a self-adjusting system, similar to the closed loop pumped hydroelectric generation system, to ensure energy generation and storage in times of deficit and excess consecutively.

1.5. Scope of the Study

This study is interested in the design, development, and implementation of a mini hydroelectric power generator at the Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun state. It will use already-developed materials that can be purchased from electrical stores and markets for construction. The findings of this project may not be restricted to the case study area, FUNAAB, but restricted to any other issue outside the topic.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0. Literature Review

2.1. Background of the Study

According to recent studies, reliable and widely affordable energy production, notably electricity, has been and continues to be a key challenge, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa (Hafner *et al.*, 2018). Nigeria is however endowed with abundant energy resources to meet its present and futuristic needs, but the inability to completely utilize available resources efficiently to generate reliable and affordable electricity for the ever-growing population is unfathomable (Oluwole *et al.*, 2021). Despite the abundance of sources of energy available for power generation, the nation remains one of the lowest electric power consumption per capita in Africa (Emovon *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 3: Three zones of access to electricity and clean cooking.

Source: Hafner *et al.* (2018).

Figure 3, adapted from Hafner *et al.* (2018), shows the three regions into which Africa is divided as he emphasized. North Africa, which is almost entirely electrified, a similar situation in South Africa (the country), which is predominantly electrified, and In the rest of sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), of which most people have no access to power (600 million) and still rely on solid biomass (wood and organic waste) for cooking (780 million). Nigeria's generation capacity is as low as 5,500MW. This is a far cry from the national electricity demand of about 40GW which results in power availability of about 6 – 12 hours per day (Diyoke *et al.*, 2022) for those with access to power thus living about 50% of the population with no electricity access (Adoghe *et al.*, 2023).

The low power generation in Nigeria has undoubtedly been the cause of her hindered economic growth and industrialization as it depends on her ability to produce reliable and adequate “quantity and quality” of power as emphasized by Emovon *et al.* (2018), and effectively distribute it to homes and industries. All the above statement needs to be understood before a sustainable solution can be proposed thus, the concept of energy/power generation in Nigeria needs to be analysed.

2.2. Power Generation

Power generation, commonly referred to as electricity production, involves employing various technologies, ranging from age-old methods like steam boilers, which have been in use for over a century, to more recent innovations like wind turbines. Technologies such as steam boilers and windmills, although traced back even further, have evolved to predominantly serve the purpose of generating electricity in contemporary times (Cummins Inc., 2022; Ibrahim *et al.*, 2023). Most power-generating equipment produce electricity by spinning a mechanism in an alternator and how they are made to spin depends on what technology is being used. An electric generator is a device that converts a form of energy into electricity, of which there are many types (Energy Information Administration, 2022).

2.2.1. Power Generation Terminologies

Before advancing into the study, some power generation terminologies must be defined to ensure transparency, consistency, Precision, clarity and understanding, as well as avoid miscommunications. The power generation terminologies are defined thus and are adopted from (Ibrahim Ozigis *et al.*, 2019);

1. Electricity Generation: The process of producing electrical energy from various sources, such as fossil fuels, renewable resources, or nuclear reactions.
2. Power Plant: A facility designed to convert a primary energy source (like coal, natural gas, or sunlight) into electrical power.
3. Renewable Energy: Energy derived from naturally replenishing sources, such as sunlight, wind, rain, tides, and geothermal heat, which are considered environmentally friendly.
4. Fossil Fuels: Non-renewable energy sources, including coal, oil, and natural gas, formed from the remains of ancient plants and animals.
5. Hydropower: Electricity is generated by harnessing the energy of flowing water, typically through dams and turbines.
6. Nuclear Power: Electricity generated by nuclear reactions, often through the fission of uranium or plutonium atoms.
7. Solar Power: Electricity generated by converting sunlight into electrical energy using photovoltaic cells or solar thermal systems.
8. Wind Power: Electricity is generated by harnessing the kinetic energy of the wind through wind turbines.
9. Geothermal Power: Electricity generated by utilizing the Earth's internal heat from geysers, hot springs, and underground reservoirs.

10. Biomass: Renewable organic materials, such as wood, crops, and waste, are used to produce energy.
11. Combined Heat and Power (CHP): A system that simultaneously generates electricity and useful thermal energy from the same energy source, increasing overall efficiency.
12. Grid: The interconnected network of power lines and substations that facilitates the distribution of electricity from power plants to consumers.
13. Capacity Factor: The ratio of the actual electrical output of a power plant to its maximum possible output under ideal conditions, often expressed as a percentage.
14. Transmission and Distribution (TandD): The processes involved in transporting electricity from power plants to end-users, including the transmission of high-voltage electricity and its distribution to homes and businesses.
15. Smart Grid: An advanced electrical grid that incorporates digital communication and control technology to enhance efficiency, reliability, and sustainability.
16. Cogeneration: Simultaneous generation of electricity and useful heat from the same energy source, optimizing energy utilization.
17. Decentralized Energy: The generation of power closer to the point of use, reducing transmission losses and improving energy efficiency.
18. Energy Storage: Technologies and systems designed to store excess energy for later use, ensuring a stable and reliable power supply.
19. Distributed Generation: Small-scale power generation units located near the point of use, providing localized energy solutions.
20. Energy Efficiency: The ratio of useful energy output to the total energy input, reflecting the effectiveness of a system in converting energy for desired purposes.

These defined terms will help us understand the subject matter as the study advances.

2.2.2. Importance of Power Generation in the Economy

Power generation holds a crucial position in the economy, serving as a fundamental element for sustainable economic progress and efforts to address and mitigate climate change (Thein and Shimada, 2023). Its significance in the economic context can be outlined as follows

1. Fostering economic growth: Energy, notably electricity, plays a crucial role in advancing sustainable economic development within societies (Hassan *et al.*, 2022).
2. Sustainable economic growth: Renewable power generation is gaining wider use for power generation around the world, driven by society's concern about environmental issues.
3. Decarbonization of electricity: The energy transition, which involves the decarbonization of electricity, is a pressing economic and ecological topic. Business research plays a crucial role in successfully mastering the decarbonization of electricity and actively shaping the energy transition (Bichler *et al.*, 2022).
4. Full costs of electricity generation: Market prices and production costs are important measures of the economics of electricity generation (Nuclear Energy Agency, 2018).

Power generation is very important to ensure the promotion of sustainable economic growth, mitigating climate change, and ensuring the successful transition to a low-carbon energy system. The importance of power generation in the economy is reflected in the growing interest in renewable energy sources and the need for business research to contribute to the decarbonization of electricity (Bichler *et al.*, 2022; Thein and Shimada, 2023).

2.2.3. Power Generation processes

There are different methods of power generation, which will be analysed in the course of this study. These different methods however undergo a common final process involving a motor or a turbine which has revolutionized the way of generating electricity (Lambda, 2023).

Figure 4: Electric Generation from an Electric turbine.

Source: U.S. Energy Information Administration (2022).

Figure 4, adapted from the U.S. Energy Information Administration (2022), illustrates the power generation process, depicting different sources of kinetic energy channelled to propel a series of blades on the rotor shaft (Energy Information Administration, 2022). The turbine then converts the source of kinetic energy (wind, steam, flowing water, etc.) into rotational energy, eventually transforming it into electrical energy through electromagnetic induction (Lambda, 2023). It is important to note that the source of kinetic energy determines the specific type of turbine to be used, which includes:

1. Wind Turbine: This converts the kinetic energy of the wind into electrical energy without causing any environmental damage (Adnan *et al.*, 2019), making it one of the most promising distributed energy sources globally (Rosly *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 5: A Wind Turbine.

Source: Saif (2019).

2. Steam Turbines: This uses a heat source such as gas, coal, nuclear, or solar to heat water to a high temperature until it turns into steam. The steam is then directed to flow past the turbine, spinning its blades and, consequently, driving the electric generator for power generation (Max, 2022).
3. Gas Turbine: Operated by burning fuels like natural gas or diesel, gas turbines produce high-pressure gas. This gas is directed onto the turbine blades, inducing rotation. The spinning blades, in turn, drive the generator, generating electrical power (Lambda, 2023).
4. Hydroelectric Turbines: Hydroelectric turbines are used in hydroelectric power plants. These turbines harness the energy from flowing or falling water to generate electricity. Usually situated in dams or rivers, hydroelectric turbines use the kinetic energy of water

to rotate their blades. The rotation of these blades drives the generator, converting the water's mechanical energy into electrical power (Lambda, 2023).

Below is a figure that shows power generation stations in Nigeria, alongside their location, plant type, years of establishment, installed units, installed capacity, and available units as explained by Samuel and Oladimeji (2020).

S/N	PLANT (A)	PLANT TYPE	LOCATION STATE (B)	AGE (YEARS) (C)	INSTALLED UNITS	INSTALLED CAPACITY (MW)	UNITS AVAILABLE	% IN- STALLED UNITS (D)
1	Egbin	Thermal	Lagos	22	6	1320	4	66.6
2	Egbin AES	Thermal	Lagos	6	9	270	9	100
3	Sapele	Thermal	Delta	25-29	10	1020	1	10
4	Okapi	Thermal	Cross River	2	3	480	2	66.6
5	Afam	Thermal	Rivers	25	20	702	3	15
6	Delta	Thermal	Delta	17	18	840	12	66.7
7	Omoku	Thermal	Rivers	2	6	150	4	66.7
8	Ajaokuta	Thermal	Kogi	Na	2	110	2	100
9	Geregu	Thermal	Kogi	1	3	414	3	100
10	Omotosho	Thermal	Ondo	New	8	335	2	50
11	Olorunsogo/ Papalanto	Thermal	Ogun	New	8	335	2	25
	SUB-TOTAL (THERMAL)				93	5976	44	47.3
12	Kainji	Hydro	Niger	38-40	8	760	6	75
13	Jebba	Hydro	Niger	24	6	540	6	100
14	Shiroro	Hydro	Niger	22	4	600	2	50
	SUB-TOTAL (HYDRO)				18	1900	14	77.78
	GRAND TOTAL				111	7876	58	52.3
SUMMARY		% Thermal			84	76	76	90.5
		% Hydro			16	24	24	

Figure 6: Existing Power Generation Capacity in Nigeria

Source: Samuel and Oladimeji (2020).

Figure 6 shows the existing power generation capacity in Nigeria. Egbin thermal station has been installed for more than 22 years. The percentage of installed units is 66.6%. Egbin AES has operated optimally at 100% in 6 years. Sapele has been operational for nearly three decades, with a functionality rate of only 10%. In contrast, Ajaokuta and Geregu have been in operation for just one year but boast a 100% functionality rate. Afam has been operational for 25 years, operating at 15%, while the new Omotoso operates at 50%. Figure 6 clearly indicates the installation years for the Okapi, Delta, and Omoka thermal stations. The mean functionality analysis for thermal stations is 47.3%.

Turning to hydropower stations, Kanji has been in operation for approximately 40 years, Jebba for 24 years, and Shiroro for 22 years. Their respective percentage of available units to installed units are 75%, 100%, and 50% (Samuel and Oladimeji, 2020; Igwe, 2021).

Upon a critical examination of this data, it becomes evident that hydroelectric power stations have a higher percentage of available or installed units, resulting in a greater amount of generated power in the country. However, issues stemming from inadequate planning within the energy sector impact the rate of power distribution, as argued by (Hafner *et al.*, 2018; Samuel and Oladimeji, 2020). This further shows that further research needs to be made in the development of more hydroelectric plants and ensure proper power generation and distribution with lesser carbon footprints and reduced ozone depletion rate.

Figure 7 below adopted from (Balcioglu *et al.*, 2017) shows the energy conversion process in various energy sources from non-renewable energy sources to solar-delivered renewable energy sources and non-solar-delivered renewable energy sources.

Figure 7: Energy conversion processes in various energy.

Source: Balcioglu *et al.* (2017).

2.3. Non-Renewable Energy

Rajeev Dhir (2023) explained non-renewable energy as those natural energy resources that cannot be replenished with speed the speed at which it is consumed or faster. As such, a non-renewable resource is a finite resource which can be generally found from the ground or a mine or generally beneath the earth. It is explained that humans constantly draw on the reserves of these substances while the formation of new supplies takes decades. Most non-renewable energy sources are fossil fuels: coal, petroleum, and natural gas (Byjus, 2024; National Geographic, 2023; Rajeev Dhir, 2023). Carbon is the main element in fossil fuels and for this reason, the period that fossil fuels formed, which is about 360-300 million years ago, is called the Carboniferous Period (National Geographic, 2023).

2.3.1. Coal

Coal has long been a significant contributor to non-renewable energy production. Coal is formed from ancient plants' remains and extracted from underground mines or surface mining methods (Byjus, 2024). Coal is mined out of the ground so it can be burnt for energy. It can be mined through underground or surface mining- when the coal mine is located below the earth's surface at about 1000 feet deep and when the mine is located very near to the surface of the earth (National Geographic, 2023). It is widely used in electricity generation and industrial processes, making it a prominent non-renewable energy resource.

2.3.2. Petroleum

Petroleum, otherwise known as liquid fuel, is derived from crude oil. Petroleum is trapped by underground rock formations. In some places, oil bubbles right out of the ground (National Geographic, 2023). Once the oil has been drilled out of its deposit, it must be refined with the help of fractional distillation of which its products are highlighted in the figure below adapted from (Karvounis and Blunt, 2021; Aboalfotouh, 2023).

Distillation product	Principal hydrocarbon families	Number of carbon atoms	% of barrel
Gasoline	Paraffins, aromatics, naphthenes	$C_{(4)} - C_{(10)}$	44
Kerosene	"	$C_{(10)} - C_{(13)}$	5
Distillate fuel oil	"	$C_{(13)} - C_{(18)}$	24
Lubricating oil	"	$C_{(18)} - C_{(45)}$	2
Residual fuel oil	Aromatics, naphthenes,	$C_{(45)}$	9
Asphalt and refinery fuel	other very complex compounds		16

Figure 8: Major Liquid Distillate Fuels derived from a Barrel of Crude Petroleum.

Source: Aboalfotouh (2023).

Only a small percentage of crude petroleum can be directly used as natural liquid fuels; but through further chemical processing, or refining, crude petroleum can yield a variety of useful fuels as well as several nonfuel products, such as greases, lubricants, and other petrochemical by-products, which can be used for firing combustion equipment and engine fuels for on-site energy systems and power generation (Aboalfotouh, 2023).

2.3.3. Natural Gas

Natural gas is another fossil fuel that is trapped underground in reservoirs, as it is mostly made up of methane. This gas can be used for heating, and cooking as well as generating electricity. This natural gas is extracted through the process of hydraulic fracturing or fracking (National Geographic, 2023). Natural gas can also be turned into a liquid form, called liquid natural gas (LNG). LNG is much cleaner than any other fossil fuel, takes up less space than its gaseous form, and can be a substitute for gasoline (Ortiz, 2022).

It is, according to research and study, that these power sources carry many issues. It is important to note that fossil fuels have played a very important role in human development however, their continuous use leads to significant environmental implications such as climate change, and air pollution caused by the burning of fossil fuels (Aboalfotouh, 2023). Harnessing nuclear energy is highly risky, while traditional fossil fuels are very quickly depleting and generate emissions such as greenhouse gasses (CO₂ among others) and contribute to economic degradation (Albezuirat *et al.*, 2021; Behera *et al.*, 2023; Akbar *et al.*, 2024). Displacing fossil fuels has become critical to environmental sustainability (Pata *et al.*, 2023).

Figure 9: The share of energy sources in electricity generation.

Source: Pata *et al.* (2023).

Data collected by Pata *et al.* (2023) shows that the percentage shares of fossil fuel is drastically increasing and a decrease in the percentage shares of modern renewables as of 2020. It is important to state that the increase in the usage of non-renewable energy will result in greater emission levels thus, affecting the environmental development, and triggering environmental

destruction processes such as ozone layer depletion, high heat records, melting of glaciers, and rise in water levels, among others. Ibadullaev *et al.* (2024) affirmed that the increase in non-renewable energy resources has a negative impact on CO₂ emission, which in turn means that the government should take measures to increase the share of renewable resources, and as suggested by Suproń and Myszczyzyn (2023), the reduction of non-renewable energy consumption will lead to the reduction of CO₂.

Carbon Dioxide contributes to 55% of global warming, with fossil fuel burning accounting for 77% and deforestation for 23% of its main sources. The atmospheric concentration of Carbon Dioxide has already undergone a nearly 30% change globally, potentially leading to an average global temperature increase of approximately 1°-5°C. Annually, the average global surface temperature rises by around 0.3°-0.6°C. Nitrogen oxides contribute to about 35% of acid rain (Booth, 2006). Methane, responsible for about 20% of the greenhouse effect, is primarily emitted through coal burning, natural gas leaks, and oil production-associated natural gas, as well as petrol spillage. In thermal power plants, the discharge of coolant water into rivers or lakes results in a sudden increase in water temperature, reducing its oxygen-holding capacity and directly impacting aquatic organisms (Nweze, 2022).

2.4. Global Consumption Patterns

The figure below, obtained from Statista, shows the number of barrels of liquid fossil fuels consumed globally from January 2020 to October 2023 in million barrels per day. Upon analysing this data, it is observed that there is a large amount of petroleum consumed with an average of 80 million barrels per day.

Figure 10: Monthly petroleum and other liquids consumption worldwide.

Source: Statista.

This means that the more petroleum consumed per day, the more the chances of carbon emission thus, leading to massive climate change rate and increased air pollution.

2.4.1. Transition to Renewable Energy Resources

The gradual transition is linked to the adverse environmental impacts associated with traditional methods of energy production and consumption, as well as the limited outputs of conventional energy sources (Nweze, 2022). Scholars contend that renewable energy stands out as the foremost energy source due to its sustainability, widespread availability, and environmentally friendly characteristics. The prominence of renewable energy lies in its role as an evolutionary form of energy to combat CO₂ emissions and address environmental degradation. Consequently, dedicated policies have been formulated to actively support the global expansion of renewable energy consumption, including initiatives targeting Africa and, more specifically, Nigeria (Joseph and Charles, 2021).

2.5. Renewable Energy Resources

Renewable energy is a type of energy that comes from sources that are naturally replenishing itself on a scale faster than the rate of consumption (Albezuirat *et al.*, 2021). Mose (2024) defines renewable energy as thus;

“Renewable energy refers to energy sources that are naturally replenished and have minimal environmental impact compared to fossil fuels” p. 4

They are available in infinite amounts because they are replaced by natural processes and forces (Khokhar, 2024). Renewable energy can be generated from a variety of sources such as wind, solar, tidal, geothermal, gravitational energy, and biomass energy (Pata *et al.*, 2023; Khokhar, 2024). In recent years, the use of fossil fuels has increased dramatically, leading to a widespread dependence on non-renewable energy sources. This trend resulted in a significant environmental consequence and to combat this, the transition of a low carbon emission source

was essential. This transition was made possible through technological innovations in the field of renewable energy (Maity *et al.*, 2023).

There are many advantages of using renewable energy, such as sustainability (cannot be depleted), ubiquity (found everywhere across the world in contrast to fossil fuels and minerals), generally non-polluting and carbon free (Albezuirat *et al.*, 2021). In addition to their major advantages, there are some disadvantages accustomed to them. The under-listed disadvantages are adopted from (Kandpal and Singh, 2022);

1. The initial setup costs are very high
2. High storage costs pose a problem for storing energy
3. It is dependent on weather conditions that may be unpredicted, causing energy shortages.
4. There is a need for a wide area for installation of renewable energy technologies.

It is suggested by Kandpal and Singh (2022) that renewable energy sources should replace fossil fuels, despite some minor challenges that need to be overcome, to meet global energy demands and shift towards cleaner energy alternatives.

The renewable energy revolution is no longer a distant dream but a tangible reality that is shaping the world's energy landscape (Khokhar, 2024), therefore three different sources of renewable energy will be critically analyzed and compared namely; solar energy, wind energy, and .

2.5.1. Solar Energy

The sun is the only source of energy for all living thing on earth as it is gotten from solar radiation (Maity *et al.*, 2023). A solar power system is one that converts the energy of the sun into thermal or electrical energy. The energy gotten from the sun can be captured through the use of photovoltaic panels, to produce heat or directly converts it to electricity (Khokhar, 2024). Solar energy is the most abundant and cleanest form of renewable energy.

This energy can be harnessed by solar technologies to generate electricity, light, and heat water for various commercial and domestic uses (Kandpal and Singh, 2022). The country is abundantly enriched with high solar energy potentials considering its geographical location as it is well positioned in a good “sunshine belt” as stated by Adebajji *et al.* (2023).

In the solar thermal system, electricity is produced by using heat energy to from the sun’s radiation which can be harnessed and concentrated using parabolic mirrors. When solar thermal power plants are employed, this solar radiation is focused on a small area to produce high-temperature steam, which is then directed to a turbine generator. This causes the generator to rotate, creating electrical energy (Maity *et al.*, 2023). Solar panels can be used to directly convert the solar radiation to electricity and then have it stored in a battery for later use.

Figure 11: Solar Tower System adopted

Source: Maity *et al.* (2023).

Below is a figure showing the solar radiation map of Nigeria, indicating that there is at least 1600 kWh/m² and a high reading of about 2200 kWh/m². Despite the abundant solar energy potentials in the counter, the percentage of solar technology applications in the energy generation mix is almost zero (Adebanji *et al.*, 2023). This lapse needs to be completely addressed in order to ensure proper electrical power supply in the country.

Figure 12: Solar Radiation Map of Nigeria.

Source: Adebajji *et al.* (2023).

Alongside the numerous advantages of solar energy, there are some pressing disadvantages attached to it. These demerits were highlighted by Maity *et al.* (2023).

1. Solar panels that are required to harvest solar energy are very expensive.
2. Solar panels produce energy in the range of 50 to 180 W, and to get a substantial amount of energy, a large number of solar panels will be required.

3. Solar panels and photovoltaic cells that are required to convert solar energy to electrical energy are non-recyclable
4. The photovoltaic cells, solar energy storage, inverters, and converters, all are high maintenance machines.
5. The amount of solar energy to be harnessed depends on the sunshine duration and season.
6. The need for a storage system.

2.5.2. Wind Energy

Wind power involves harnessing the energy of the wind through the use of wind turbines to generate electricity. These turbines convert the kinetic energy of the wind into electrical power (Khokhar, 2024). Wind power is an increasingly popular sustainable, renewable energy source that impacts the environment much less than burning fossil fuels and other types of renewable sources (Kandpal and Singh, 2022). The development of larger and more efficient wind turbines has enabled the production of clean electricity on a large scale by utilizing Earth's wind currents (Khokhar, 2024).

This energy production technique does not require any fuel, making it an appropriate option for those looking to reduce their carbon footprint. Additionally, wind power is becoming increasingly cost-effective due to technological advancements, enhancing its efficiency and reliability (Kandpal and Singh, 2022; Maity *et al.*, 2023). The wind energy sector has become a significant contributor to the global economy, remaining resilient even in the face of rising fossil fuel prices. With a 16.4% share in 2014 and a subsequent 0.8% increase to 17.2% in 2015, wind power leads the way in environmentally friendly power generation worldwide (Balcioglu *et al.*, 2017; Mose, 2024).

Despite its global growth, the installed wind energy capacity in Africa lags behind other regions, as illustrated in the figure analyzed by Akporhonor *et al.* (2023). This deficiency is attributed to various challenges, including poor maintenance, insecurity, and insufficient investment.

Figure 13: Installed Wind Capacity.

Source: Akporhonor *et al.* (2023).

The installed capacity of wind energy in Nigeria was further analysed and a discovery was made as indicated in the figure below as Nigeria has a very minute percentage of installed wind capacity thus contributing to the power challenges faced. (Figures were gotten from Statista)

Figure 14: Installed wind energy capacity in Africa gotten from Statista.

2.5.3. Hydropower Energy

Hydropower refers to the extraction of hydraulic energy from falling water, determined by its velocity, position, or both. The turbine blade surfaces experience a differential force, leading to rotary motion, due to the rate of change of angular momentum or pressure (or both) of the falling water (Kaunda *et al.*, 2012). This can be achieved with or without dams (Kandpal and Singh, 2022). In a hydropower system, water, serving as the working fluid, is not consumed and remains available for other purposes. Hydropower is a clean and non-polluting source of energy. It operates at a low maintenance cost. It has a 90 per cent conversion rate, making hydropower one of the most efficient sources of energy (Akashie, 2022; Kandpal and Singh, 2022).

Large-scale hydropower plants are normally used for electricity generation, and to generate electricity, the turbine output shaft is connected to the generator, which consists mainly of an electromagnetic rotor situated within a cylinder, known as the stator, housing a winding of electric wires, referred to as the conductor. In the course of operation, the rotating rotor within the stator produces electricity through the process of electromagnetic induction (Kaunda *et al.*, 2012). The basic schematic diagram for the hydroelectric power generation system is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Schematic view of a hydropower station adopted from Kkaunda *et al.* (2012)

- | | | |
|---------------|------------------------|------------------------|
| 1. Reservoir | 6. Tailrace | 11. Transformer |
| 2. Penstock | 7. Turbine | 12. Insulators |
| 3. Bedrock | 8. Generator | 13. Transmission Tower |
| 4. Valve | 9. Powerhouse | 14. Trash Rack |
| 5. Draft tube | 10. Transmission Lines | |

The effective energy output at a dam is influenced by two key factors: the volume of water released (discharge) and the vertical distance the water descends (head). Therefore, a specific

quantity of water falling a particular distance will yield a specific amount of energy (Algburi and Sharma, 2016). The choice of turbine is determined by the head, discharge, and the desired rotational speed of the generator at the power site. The head generates water pressure, and a higher head results in increased pressure to drive the turbines (Khayal, 2019).

To find how much electrical power we can expect, we must convert the mechanical measure (horsepower) into electrical terms (watts). One horsepower is equal to 746 watts (U.S. measure) (Khayal, 2019).

2.5.3.1. A Pumped Storage Hydropower Plant

Practically, in terms of both design and economics, pumped storage technology is stated to be the only large form of grid-based electric energy storage currently available to the power utility (Kaunda *et al.*, 2012). Pumped storage is water pumped to a storage pool above the power plant at a time when customer demand for energy is low, such as during the middle of the night. The water is then allowed to flow back through the turbine-generators at times when demand is high and a heavy load is placed on the system (Khayal, 2019). This system has an important advantage as the hydroelectric generating units can start up quickly and make rapid adjustments in output, and the construction costs are very low since they are relatively small compared with conventional hydropower facilities (Karre *et al.*, 2022).

In conclusion, the proposed project will follow the same principle of development as of a pump storage hydropower plant as indicated below.

Figure 16: A Pump Storage Hydro-powered System.

Source: Viadero *et al.* (2017).

Figure 17 is an example of a mini hydroelectric power generator adopted from Ogochukwu (2012).

Figure 17: The Mini-Hydroelectric Power Generator.

Source: Ogochukwu (2012).

CHAPTER THREE

3.0. Materials and Methods

3.1. Materials

The mini hydroelectric power generator and energy storage system consist of parts that can convert the rotational properties of the hydroelectric turbine to electrical energy for use as well as storage while ensuring efficiency, effectiveness, and sustainability. The major components of the mini hydroelectric generator are:

1. A 12V DC Electric Generator
2. ½ Inch Square Metal Pipe
3. ¾ Inch 90⁰ Plastic Elbow
4. ¾ Inch Plastic Pipe
5. ¾ Inch Sockets
6. ¾ Inch Adapter
7. Digital Multimeter
8. A Valve
9. A Water Wheel.
10. Storage Tanks.

The tools that will be used are:

1. Screwdriver sets: The screwdriver sets will be used to operate screws on the components during assembly.
2. Cutters: Cutters will be used to cut smaller and thinner wires that are too thin for the pliers to cut. In addition, the cutters were also used to cut the electrical tape.
3. Electrical tapes: Will be used to protect all exposed wire-to-wire connections.

4. Pliers: Pliers will be used to cut wires, and peel out the insulation on wires to aid connections and soldering.
5. Hot-glue gun: This will be used in the assembly of the plastic pipes for firm fitting, and also to close up holes made in the reservoir during the piping process.
6. Digital multi-meter: The digital multi-meter will be used to measure the currents and voltage produced by the hydroelectric power generator. The values obtained will then be used to calculate the output power.

Plate 1: A Digital Multimeter

7. PVC Bonding Adhesive: This will be used to hold the internal surfaces of plastic fittings in place during the piping process.

8. Size 10 Spanner: This will be used to operate bolts and nuts through the reservoir to the hydroelectric turbine frame during coupling.
9. 10mm Bolt and Nut: This will be used to hold the bottom reservoir to the frame of the hydroelectric power generator during the coupling process.

The power tools that will be used are:

1. The Angle Grinder: This will be used to cut workpieces to desirable sizes using the cutting blade and also grinding welded surfaces of the frame for smoothening using the grinding disc.
2. Power Hand Drill: This will be used to make dimensioned holes in the overhead reservoir for pipe fitting and to drill the hydroelectric generator's frame to retrofit the bottom reservoir with the bolts and nuts.
3. Arc welder: This will be used in the construction process for joining parts of the frame materials together to form a rigid body for the other parts to be fitted in.

3.2. Design Analysis

Figure 18: Block Diagram of Water Flow Process.

Source: Okhueleigbe and Ofualagba (2017).

3.3. Design of the Major Components

The Major components designs are

1. The Overhead reservoirs
2. The Water Wheel
3. The Frame Structure

3.3.1. Overhead Reservoir Design

The water storage tank is the place where the required quantity of water, capable enough to start the water wheel motion process, is stored. The water storage tank is always located at a higher level as compared to the position of all other constructed structures as its height determines how much potential energy the falling water will possess. The greater the height, the more the potential energy the volume of water will possess, and the more it turns the turbine of the hydropower generator.

Potential Energy PE is represented in the equation 1

$$PE = mgh \text{ (Joules) -----(1)}$$

Equation 1: Potential Energy

Where: m = mass (kg)

g = acceleration due to gravity (9.81m/s^2)

h = height/ head (m)

Determining the mass of water requires evaluation through density formula

$$Density = \frac{Mass}{Volume} \text{ (kg/m}^3\text{) -----(2)}$$

Equation 2: Density Formula

$$Mass = Density * Volume \text{ (kg)}$$

Given that the test volume of the overhead reservoir is chosen to be 100 litres for efficient potential energy generation for low head and ease for upscale as suggested by Carruthers *et al.* (2018), as well as the head elevation of 2.5m will be utilised for this experiment as suggested by Carruthers *et al.* (2018).

Where; $1\text{m}^3 = 1000\text{l}$

Thus, $100l = 0.1m^3$

Density of water is assumed to be 1000 kg/m^3

Therefore, the mass of water is 100kg , and using equation 1, the potential energy from a 2.5m is 2452.5J which is capable enough to turn the newly designed water mill in order to turn the electric generator accordingly .

According to Okhueigbe and Ofualagba (2017), the outflow from the tank was estimated by calculations using the formula,

$$V = Cv\sqrt{2gH} \text{-----}(3)$$

Equation 3: Kinetic and Potential energy formula as adopted

Source: Okhueigbe and Ofualagba (2017).

Where: V = Velocity of flow

g = The Acceleration due to gravity

H = Head

Cv = coefficient of velocity ranging from 0.14 to 0.95

The size of the water storage tank used is 100liters

The calculated velocity of flow will, according to equation 4, be:

$$V_{\text{theoretical}} = 0.27 * \sqrt{2 * 9.81 * 2.5} = 1.89 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$$

3.3.2. Penstock Design

The penstock is the course at which the water passes to the turbine. They are made of concrete (only for low heads of less than 30m), steel (for any head), as emphasised by Kader *et al.* (2016). The PVC penstock will consist of PVC pipe sections, elbow joints, valves, and a nozzle, creating a connection between the water storage tank and the turbine wheel. The PVC material

is used due to the fact that the scale of the project is minimal as compared to the full scale and also to reduce, to the barest minimum, the amount of losses in the pipe flow due to frictional forces and fittings. The penstock is essential in the calculation of the flow rate or discharge of water.

According to Kumar and Singhal (2015), designing the penstock for optimisation must factor in certain characteristics such as reduction in frictional loss and other losses such as special losses due to bends, transition pieces, among others. Their extensive research and experimentations using Chezy Formula for frictional losses and Darcy Weisbach frictional loss relationship shows that the greater the penstock diameter, the lesser the frictional losses and the more the discharge. However, this observation changes with material used. Therefore, PVC pipes will have a reduced frictional loss if it falls in the range of 0.1m to 0.3m in diameter which suggests the use of 0.2m diameter PVC pipe summing up to ¾ of an inch.

A ¾ inch with uniform diameter tailstock will be used with 15mm nozzle.

$$1\text{inch} = 2.54\text{cm} = 25.4\text{mm}$$

$$\frac{3}{4}\text{ inch} = 19.05\text{mm} = 1.905\text{cm}$$

Calculating the area (A_1) of the penstock using area formula

$$A_1 = A_2 = \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \text{-----(4)}$$

$$A_1 = A_2 = 3.142 \frac{(19.05\text{mm})^2}{4} = 0.000285\text{m}^2$$

Equation 4: Area Formula

The area (A_3) of the nozzle is given by:

$$A_3 = \frac{\pi d^2}{4} = 3.142 \frac{(13\text{mm})^2}{4} = 0.000133\text{m}^2$$

Where: A_1 = Cross-sectional area of the penstock inlet (m^2)

A_2 = Cross-sectional area of the penstock outlet (m^2)

A_3 = Cross-sectional area of the nozzle (m^2)

D_1 = Diameter of the Penstock (mm)

D_2 = Diameter of the Penstock (mm)

d = Diameter of the nozzle

Calculating the water flow through the penstock, noting that the velocity of flow will remain the same at the inlet of the penstock and at the end of the penstock provided that there are no losses due to contraction, expansion, bends, and fittings. Using the Equation 5 will verify the velocity of flow in the penstock.

$$A_1V_1 = A_2V_2 \text{ -----(5)}$$

Equation 5: Continuity Equation

Source: Thomas *et al.* (2020)

Since A_1 and A_2 of the penstock are equal,

$$V_1 = V_2 = 1.89m/s$$

Therefore, calculating the flow rate at the penstock using the Flow-rate Formula.

$$Q = AV$$

Equation 6: Flow-rate Formula

Source: Ghadban (2023)

$$Q = 0.000285m^2 * 1.89m/s$$

$$Q = 0.000539 \frac{m^3}{s}$$

Therefore, using the flow-rate formula, the velocity at the nozzle to turn the turbine is:

$$Q = A_3 V$$

$$0.000539 = 0.000133 \times V_o$$

$$V_o = 4.05\text{m/s}$$

Where V_o is the Velocity of flow from the nozzle (m/s)

Justifying the size of the conduit pipe penstock, according to Ajibola *et al.* (2018), his research focussed on improving the existing water wheel for power generation of which his values are utilised. However, the size of the penstock used was taken to be a diameter of 5m and according to the scale of this project as compared to his standards, a rate of 1: 1500 will be used of which what ever value is determined as the velocity from the penstock and the discharge form it will then be scaled up by 1500 times to determine the original power of the full scale project (Alonso, 2024).

3.3.3. Water Wheel Design

If the speed of rotation of the turbine id given by (N) and the net head (H) and water flow are known, the dimension of the water wheel can be estimated from the following equations (Nasir, 2013, 2014; Yumpu, 2014).

$$D_1 = 40.8 * \frac{\sqrt{H_n}}{N} \text{-----}(7)$$

Equation 7: Diameter of the circle describing the buckets centre line in meters (Runner Diameter)

Source: Nasir (2013, 2014)

$$B_2 = 1.68 * \sqrt{\frac{Q}{K}} * \sqrt{\frac{1}{\sqrt{H_n}}} \text{-----}(8)$$

Equation 8: Bucket width in meters

Source: Yumpu (2014)

Where K = number of nozzles.

According to Nasir (2013), the ratio of D_1 and B_2 must always be greater than 2.7. If this is false, then calculations for more number of nozzles should be carried out.

Given through observation, the converted induction motor, at the water discharge speed, spins at a certain rpm, and taking the head to be 2.5m, and the diameter of the circle describing the buckets centreline (D_1) is measured to be 0.3m, using equation 7 is given by:

$$D_1 = 40.8 * \frac{\sqrt{2.5}}{N} = 0.30m$$

Therefore the number of evolution per minute is

$$N = 215.8 \text{ rpm (Theoretical)}$$

The bucket width (B_2), using equation 9, is also given as:

$$B_2 = 1.68 * \sqrt{\frac{0.000539}{1}} * \sqrt{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2.5}}} = 0.031m.$$

The number of nozzles (K) is 1.

Therefore, the D_1/B_1 ratio is:

$$\frac{0.3m}{0.031m} = 9.68 > 2.7.$$

Thus, the design for the water wheel is feasible using one nozzle.

A turbine bucket of 0.1m will be used to improve its coverage area.

3.3.3.1. Design for the Water Wheel Blades

According to Okhueleigbe and Ofualagba (2017), choosing the right number of blades is crucial when designing a Turbine Runner. A lower blade count can lead to the turbine not fully utilizing the available water, while an excessive number of blades may result in pulsating power and a decrease in turbine efficiency.

$$\text{Number of Blades} = 8$$

Appropriate blade spacing is essential to ensure that water efficiently strikes the blades for optimal thrust production. The specific blade spacing is determined by the number of blades incorporated into the turbine runner (Nasir, 2014). The blades will be positioned in an air foil shape in order for it to allow water flow horizontally into it, making a greater volume of water to be handled per rotation.

$$Blade\ Spacing = \frac{360}{number\ of\ blades} \text{-----}(9)$$

Equation 9: Blade spacing Formula.

Source: Okhueleigbe and Ofualagba (2017).

$$Blade\ Spacing = \frac{360}{8} = 45^{\circ}$$

This water wheel design is used because of the similarity in Carruthers *et al.* (2018) operational parameters. However, given the scale of this project the original size of the water wheel will be scaled down with a ratio of 1:38 in order to get a diameter of 0.38m.

A water wheel is designed due to the research made by Carruthers *et al.* (2018) that suggests advantages of an efficient water wheel.

1. The water wheel ensures smooth flow that reduces turbulence thus reducing energy loss which also allows fish farming and lower land usage.
2. Installation in urban sites, reducing transmission losses.

It is wrongly assumed that fundamental water wheel design cannot be improved, with only evolution rather than revolution. Therefore, adjusting the inlets of the water wheel can increase rotational power and speed thus increasing power output. Instead of just allowing water strike the blades of the water wheel, the new design will allow water flow horizontally deep into the blades, allowing greater volume to be handled per rotation.

The blade angle is an important factor to consider when designing an efficient water wheel as stated by Zaman and Khan (2012). The extensive research made by Kodirov *and* Tursunov (2019) showed that for maximum efficiency, the blade angle to the horizontal should be $\alpha = 16^\circ$ as illustrated in Figure 20.

Figure 19: Efficient Water Wheel

Source: (Carruthers *et al.*, 2018)

Where;

1. Water Flow
2. Frame Installation
3. Housing
4. Blades
5. Shaft

6. Steel Core

Plate 2: Fabricated 8 Blade Water Wheel Unit

3.3.4. Power Output

Calculating the power that would be produced from the generator using a 12V DC Generator, from a 2.5m elevation head will involve the extensive use of Bernoulli's principle, an important theory in fluid mechanics developed by Daniel Bernoulli (Qin and Duan, 2017), to determine the energy taking out of the flow.

Bernoulli's Equation is stated as follows,

$$Z + \frac{P}{\rho g} + \frac{V^2}{2g} = \text{Constant} \text{-----(10)}$$

Equation 10: Bernoulli's Equation

Source: Dourmashkin (2020)

Where;

Z = Elevation Head (m)

$\frac{P}{\rho g}$ = Pressure Head (m)

$\frac{V^2}{2g}$ = Velocity Head (m)

However, in calculations, there are losses that will be incurred due to the flow of water in the pipe such as frictional losses, and local losses (Fittings). These losses, as well as the energy taking out of the flow (ΔH) need to be factored into Bernoulli's Equation at equation 11.

Therefore, the equation then becomes;

$$Z_1 + \frac{P_1}{\rho g} + \frac{V_1^2}{2g} - \text{Losses} - (\Delta H) = Z_2 + \frac{P_2}{\rho g} + \frac{V_2^2}{2g} \text{-----(11)}$$

Equation 11: Bernoulli's Equation Expanded

Source: Dourmashkin (2020)

Where,

P = Pressure (N/m²)

Z = Elevation (m)

V = Velocity (m/s)

ρ = Density (Kg/m³)

g = Acceleration Due to Gravity (9.81 m/s²)

The losses that resulted from the flow of water in the pipe are given in the Darcy Weisbach Equation.

$$\text{Frictional Loss} = f \frac{l v^2}{d 2g} \text{ (m)} \text{-----(12)}$$

Equation 12: Frictional Loss

Source: Patel et al. (2018)

If the length of the pipe is 2m, coefficient of friction is 0.02, and all other parameters are already determined, computations will result to having the frictional losses amount to,

$$H_f = 0.02 \times \frac{2 \times 1.89^2}{0.01905 \times 2 \times 9.81}$$

$$H_f = 0.38m$$

Since the pressure at the top of the reservoir equals atmospheric pressure, the pressure head there resolves to zero. Additionally, the velocity at the top of the reservoir is negligible compared to the velocity of water in the penstock (pipe), so the velocity head at the reservoir will be zero as well. At point 2, which is the turbine location, the elevation is equal to ground level elevation, hence zero. Similarly, the pressure head at the outlet is zero as it discharges at atmospheric pressure.

Then, equation 11 becomes,

$$\Delta H = Z_1 - H_f - \frac{v_2^2}{2g} \text{-----(13)}$$

Where Z_1 = head elevation + height of water in tank

$$Z_1 = 2.5m + 1.3m$$

Equation 13: Bernoulli's Equation (Modified)

$$\Delta H = 3.8 - 0.38 - \frac{1.89^2}{2 * 9.81}$$

$$\Delta H = 3.24m$$

Calculating the power generated from the generator, the following formula is used.

$$P = \rho g Q \Delta H \eta \text{ -----(14)}$$

Equation 14: Theoretical Power of a Generator

Source: P Velmurugan *et al.* (2021)

Where,

P = Power of the Generator (W)

Q = Discharge (m³/s)

η = Efficiency of the Turbine (80%)

ρ = Density of Water (1000kg/m³)

Therefore,

$$P = 1000 \times 9.81 \times 0.000539 \times 3.24 \times 0.8$$

$$P_{Theoretical} = 14W$$

3.3.5. Power Rating of the Pump

To maintain a consistent water head for water circulation and ensure an uninterrupted water supply during testing, it becomes necessary to employ a pump that can transfer water from the lower reservoir back up to an additional storage tank below the overhead tank and above ground level, compensating for any decrease in water level. This entails calculating the appropriate rating and power requirements for the pump, specifically to lift water from the lower reservoir to the storage tank, accounting for the vertical height disparity of (This will be 2.2m) meters between the two reservoirs.

The formula for calculating the power of a pump is given thus, according to Amir Razmi (2019).

$$\text{Power of the pump} = Q\rho gh \text{ (Watts)} \text{-----}(15)$$

Equation 15: Power of a Pump

Source: Sowby *and* Krieger (2023)

Where;

Q = Discharge (m^3/s)

ρ = Density of water ($1000\text{kg}/\text{m}^3$)

g = Acceleration due to Gravity (m/s^2)

Power of the pump = 7 *Watts*

This power is approximately 50% of the power produced by the turbine where the remaining 50% will be used to charge the battery for energy storage.

A battery will be added to the circuit as a voltage source to supply power to the pump at designated intervals until a specified volume of water is lifted to the storage reservoir, for energy storage, which will now be used to further produce power in times of insufficient power production from other sources.

3.4. Diagrammatic Representation of the Setup

Figure 20: Diagrammatic Representation of Set Up

Plate 3: Assembled Project Materials for Testing

3.5. Construction Process

A plastic pipe measuring three-quarters of an inch in diameter is slated to be affixed to the underside of a 100-liter plastic water tank, with the addition of a valve for regulating the discharge at the pipe's terminus. The strategic positioning of the water tank at an elevation of 2.5 meters above ground level is intended to amplify its potential energy, consequently augmenting the kinetic energy of the ensuing flow. This setup will be documented comprehensively with accompanying pictorial documentation throughout the construction phase.

At ground level, a reservoir with a capacity of 50 litres will be securely positioned within a framework, serving to capture the cascading water for subsequent utilization in propelling a water wheel. Subsequently, this water wheel will be intricately linked to a magnetically induced motor, which entails the affixation of neodymium magnets to its poles to instigate the generation of electric current.

Furthermore, a pump, meticulously selected based on calculated specifications, will play a pivotal role in the system by facilitating the restoration of the water volume to the elevated reservoir. This replenishment mechanism will be triggered when the water level within the lower reservoir attains a predetermined threshold, a parameter that will be fine-tuned during rigorous testing procedures.

3.6. Testing and Data Collection

Following the completion of the setup, a sequential methodology will be implemented to address the initial research inquiries. Specifically, the functionality of the generator will undergo rigorous testing to ascertain its voltage and current output across varying discharge rates at 0° , 30° , 60° and 90° of opening, as well as water volumes prior to the commencement of water pumping activities.

Throughout the testing phase, meticulous measurements will be conducted to gauge the generator's performance under different operational parameters. This will involve assessing its voltage and current output levels at discrete intervals, with a particular focus on discerning any fluctuations or trends associated with varying discharge rates and water volumes.

Subsequently, as the water pumping process is initiated, a parallel assessment will be carried out to evaluate the real-time voltage and current output of the generator. This comprehensive evaluation aims to delineate the actual utility of the generated electrical power for external applications.

Using the $P = I \times V$ (Watts), the power produced will be found at every one-minute interval.

$$P = I \times V \text{-----(16)}$$

Equation 16: Power Output

The actual efficiency of the turbine turbine will therefore be determined using the $\eta_{calculated}$ = $\frac{P_{output}}{P_{rated}}$ formula.

$$\eta_{calculated} = \frac{P_{output}}{P_{rated}} \text{-----(17)}$$

Equation 17: Calculated Efficiency of Machine

3.7. Analysis of Acquired Data

The collected data on the output voltage and current, obtained at various discharge rates before and during the pumping process, will be organized and fed into analysis software. This software will then produce graphical representations illustrating the relationships between current, voltage, and discharge. These visuals will offer insights into the system's performance dynamics, aiding in optimization and further development.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0. Result and Discussion

4.1. Measured Data

The set-up was made and thoroughly checked to ensure that all parts were perfectly fitting and that there were no leakages in the joints of the pipes and the outlets of the reservoirs. The fittings were well tightened using a wrench and when all leakages have been stopped and all fittings have been placed in their respective positions, two tests were carried out.

The first test was to determine the discharge from the overhead reservoir and the storage reservoir at different angles of the opening of the outlet valve. Upon calibration of the valve, a 0° , 30° , 60° and 90° opening angle was used to determine the individual discharge represented in Table 1 and Table 2 for reservoirs 1 and 2 respectively.

4.1.1. Discharge Determination

Reservoir 1

Table 1: Discharge of the Overhead Reservoir at Varying Angles

<i>Angle</i> ($^\circ$)	<i>Volume</i> (L)	<i>Time</i> (s)	<i>Discharge</i> (m^3/s)	<i>Discharge</i> (l/s)
0	0	0	Nil	Nil
30	2	5	0.0004	0.4
60	4	5	0.0008	0.8
90	6	5	0.0012	1.2

Where;

Angle is in degrees,

Volume is in Liters,

Time is in Seconds, and

Discharge is in $\frac{l}{s}$ and in $\frac{m^3}{s}$.

Reservoir 2

Table 2: Discharge of the Storage Reservoir at Varying Angles

<i>Angle</i> (°)	<i>Volume</i> (L)	<i>Time</i> (s)	<i>Discharge</i> (<i>m³/s</i>)	<i>Discharge</i> (<i>l/s</i>)
0	0	0	Nil	Nil
30	1.5	5	0.0003	0.3
60	3	5	0.0006	0.6
90	4.5	5	0.0009	0.09

4.1.2. Power Generation Test at Reservoir 1

Reservoir 1, the overhead reservoir was filled with water either manually or by natural precipitation, serving as the natural source of water in a sustainable city. The outlet valve was then opened at different angles, suggesting different discharges. This falling water with potential energy is directed towards the blades of the water wheel, which is connected to the 12 Volt DC generator. The resulting voltage and current output at 1-minute intervals, upon replenishment of the overhead reservoir to ensure a partly constant head, was measured using a multimeter and entered into Tables 2, 3, and 4, of discharges, corresponding to the opening angle of 30°, 60°, and 90° respectively.

At a 30° angle, Table 3 was derived.

Where ;

$$Power = Current (I) \times Voltage (V) \text{ ----- (18)}$$

$$Workdone = Current (I) \times Voltage (V) \times Time (T) \text{ -----(19)}$$

Table 3: Preliminary Output Test for Reservoir 1 at Partially Opened (30°) for 10minutes

Voltage (v)	Current (A)	Time (s)	Power (W)	Work done (J)
0.92	0.07	60	0.064	3.86
1.17	0.09	60	0.11	6.32
1.61	0.09	60	0.15	8.69
1.62	0.1	60	0.16	9.72
2.1	0.24	60	0.5	30.24
1.94	0.31	60	0.6	36.08
2.22	0.42	60	0.93	55.94
2.51	0.46	60	1.15	69.28
2.76	0.5	60	1.38	82.8
2.27	0.38	60	0.86	51.76

Figure 20 shows the relationship between current and voltage output at partially opened valve discharge.

Figure 21: Current and Voltage Output at Partially Opened Valve (30°)

At 60° angle, Table 4 was derived.

Table 4: Preliminary Output Test for Reservoir 1 at Half Opened (60°) for 10 minutes

Voltage (v)	Current (A)	Time (s)	Power (W)	Work done (J)
3.14	0.68	60	2.14	128.11
2.78	0.88	60	2.45	146.78
3.13	0.72	60	2.25	135.22
3.46	0.22	60	0.76	45.67
3.67	0.82	60	3.01	180.56
4	0.79	60	3.16	189.6
3.66	0.9	60	3.29	197.4
3.99	0.9	60	3.6	215.46
2.28	0.59	60	1.36	80.71
3.41	0.34	60	1.16	69.56

Figure 21 shows the relationship between current and voltage output at half opened valve discharge.

Figure 22: Current and Voltage Output at Half Opened Valve (60°) Discharge

At 90° angle, Table 5 was derived.

Table 5: Preliminary Output Test for Reservoir 1 at Fully Opened (90°) for 10 minutes

Voltage (v)	Current (A)	Time (s)	Power (W)	Work done (J)
3.41	0.62	60	2.11	126.85
3.98	0.51	60	2.03	121.78
4.24	0.92	60	3.9	234.05
5.1	1	60	5.1	306
5.21	1.1	60	5.73	343.86
6.42	0.94	60	6.03	362.09
6.89	1.49	60	10.27	615.97
7	1.48	60	10.36	621.6
6.9	1.5	60	10.35	621
5.42	1.23	60	6.67	400

Figure 22 shows the relationship between current and voltage output at fully opened valve discharge.

Figure 23: Current and Voltage Output at Fully Opened Valve (90°) Discharge

4.1.3. Power Generation Test at Reservoir 2 (Storage Reservoir)

During the testing procedure, the water was first drawn from an overhead reservoir and subsequently collected in a ground-level reservoir equipped with a submerged pump. This setup simulates a small-scale hydroelectric system, which can play a crucial role in sustainable cities by balancing energy supply and demand.

In sustainable urban environments, energy demands fluctuate throughout the day and across different seasons. For instance, during the summer months, when solar radiation is at its peak, solar panels generate excess energy that surpasses the immediate consumption needs of the city. Similarly, during periods of high wind velocity, wind turbines can produce more energy than required. Additionally, nighttime often sees a significant reduction in energy consumption as most residents are inactive, leading to further excess energy generation.

To prevent this surplus energy from going to waste, the excess power generated during these low-demand periods can be redirected to the hydroelectric system. Specifically, the surplus electricity is used to operate the submerged pump, which transfers water from the ground-level reservoir back up to the overhead storage tank. This process effectively stores energy in the form of potential energy within the elevated water, creating a reserve that can be utilized when the city experiences higher energy demands.

During periods of high energy demand—such as in winter, when heating requirements increase, or during times of low wind velocity when wind energy production decreases—this stored water can be released from the overhead tank. As the water flows back down to the lower reservoir, it passes through turbines that generate electricity, thereby supplementing the city's energy needs during these critical times. This process is especially valuable during drought periods when the natural water supply is insufficient for conventional hydroelectric power generation.

By incorporating such a hydroelectric system into the city's energy infrastructure, the city can efficiently manage and store excess renewable energy, ensuring a consistent and reliable power supply throughout the year. This system not only optimizes the use of renewable energy sources but also contributes to reducing the reliance on non-renewable energy during peak demand periods. The strategic use of surplus energy for water pumping also enhances the overall resilience and sustainability of the city's power grid, making it better equipped to handle

fluctuations in energy production and consumption. Therefore the potential for storage is tested. An overall of 5.75V at 1.2A (6.9 Watts) was used to pump the water to the storage reservoir for further generation. The following data was obtained during testing at various discharges.

At 30° opened valve equivalent discharge, Table 6 was obtained.

Table 6: Preliminary Output Test for Storage Reservoir at Partly Opened (30°) for 10 minutes

Voltage (v)	Current (A)	Time (s)	Power (W)	Work done (J)
0.09	0.01	60	0.0001	0.054
0.1	0.07	60	0.007	0.42
0.23	0.11	60	0.025	1.52
0.38	0.09	60	0.034	2.05
0.54	0.13	60	0.07	4.21
0.56	0.21	60	0.118	7.06
0.7	0.29	60	0.203	12.18
0.91	0.3	60	0.273	16.38
0.78	0.26	60	0.203	12.17
0.88	0.14	60	0.123	7.39

Figure 23 shows the relationship between current and voltage output at partly opened valve equivalent discharge.

Figure 24: Storage Current and Voltage Output at Partly Opened Valve (30°) Discharge

At 60° opened valve equivalent discharge, Table 7 was obtained.

Table 7: Preliminary Output Test for Storage Reservoir at Half Opened (60°) for 10 minutes

Voltage (v)	Current (A)	Time (s)	Power (W)	Work done (J)
1.11	0.2	60	0.22	13.32
1.52	0.41	60	0.62	37.39
1.43	0.43	60	0.61	36.89
1.96	0.48	60	0.94	56.45
2.1	0.64	60	1.34	80.64
2	0.66	60	1.32	79.2
2.58	0.84	60	2.17	130.03
3	0.97	60	2.91	174.6
2.62	0.9	60	2.36	141.48
2.79	0.96	60	2.68	160.7

Figure 24 shows the relationship between current and voltage output at half opened valve equivalent discharge.

Figure 25: Storage Current and Voltage Output at Half Opened Valve (60°) Discharge

At 90° opened valve equivalent discharge, Table 8 was obtained.

Table 8: Preliminary Output Test for Storage Reservoir at Fully Opened (90°) for 10 minutes

Voltage (v)	Current (A)	Time (s)	Power (W)	Work done (J)
1.18	0.13	60	0.15	9.2
1.29	0.33	60	0.43	25.8
2.12	0.42	60	0.89	53.4
2.54	0.48	60	1.22	73.14
2.98	0.67	60	1.2	119.8
3.49	1.13	60	3.94	236.62
3.1	1.02	60	3.16	189.72
4.01	1.43	60	5.73	344.06
3.62	1.15	60	4.16	249.78
3.14	1.09	60	3.42	205.36

Figure 25 shows the relationship between current and voltage output at fully opened valve equivalent discharge.

Figure 26: Storage Current and Voltage Output at Fully Opened Valve (90°) Discharge

4.1.4. Maximum Power Determination and Comparison

According to the already obtained data, the maximum power expended and obtained will be analysed to determine the storage potential of the storage reservoir. The maximum power for each discharge and reservoirs are shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Power, Discharge and Voltage Relationship of Reservoir 1 and the Storage Reservoir

Discharge Angle	Reservoir 1			Storage Reservoir		
	Power Output (W)	Discharge (l/s)	Work Done (J)	Power Output (W)	Discharge (l/s)	Work Done (J)
0	Nil	0	0	Nil	0	0
30	1.38	0.4	82.8	0.27	0.3	16.38
60	3.6	0.8	215.46	2.91	0.6	174.6
90	10.36	1.2	621.6	5.73	0.9	344.06

With 6.9 watts of power expended to get the required volume of water to the storage reservoir, the overall power generated and saved is illustrated in Figure 26.

Given that approximately 7 Watts of power was used, and the maximum power generated was 10.36 Watts, leaving approximately 3.36 watts of power and also creating a potential 5.73 Watts and a total saved power of 9.09 watts. Therefore, the hydroelectric generation and storage system was able to generate power and also save power that can be utilised in periods of peak power demands.

Power and Workdone Relationship Upon Discharge

Figure 27: Power and Workdone Relationship upon Discharge

4.2. Calculated Data

4.2.1. Systems Efficiencies

Determining the efficiency of power generated and power stored, the theoretical power will be taken into consideration, as well as the experimental power for both the overhead reservoir and the storage reservoir. The efficiency formula as shown below will be utilised.

$$\text{Efficiency of the Machine} = \frac{\text{Experimental Power}}{\text{Theoretical Power}} \text{-----}(20)$$

Therefore, efficiency of the Overhead reservoir for power generation (E_{og}) is given by:

$$E_{og} = \frac{10.36}{14} \times 100\%$$

$$E_{og} = 74\%$$

The Efficiency of the Overall power stored by the system after the power expended to pump water to the storage tank is removed (E_{sg}), is given by:

$$E_{sg} = \frac{9.09}{14} \times 100\%$$

$$E_{sg} = 64.93\%$$

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0. Recommendations and Conclusion

5.1. Conclusion

This research examined the potential of a small-scale hydroelectric power generation and storage system in sustainable cities. The study tested how well the system could generate and store energy by varying the opening angles of the valves in the water reservoirs. The results showed that the system was able to generate a maximum of 10.36 watts of power from the overhead reservoir when the valve was fully opened at a 90° angle. The storage reservoir also produced a maximum of 5.73 watts under the same conditions. After accounting for the power used to pump the water back to the storage reservoir, the system was still able to save about 9.09 watts of power, which could be used during times of high energy demand, such as in winter, during low wind periods, or at night.

The findings suggest that small-scale hydroelectric systems can play a significant role in making cities more energy-efficient and less dependent on non-renewable energy sources. By storing excess energy generated during low-demand periods, like at night or during sunny or windy conditions, and using it during high-demand periods, cities can ensure a steady and reliable power supply throughout the year. This approach not only helps in managing energy resources more effectively but also contributes to the overall sustainability of urban environments.

5.2. Limitations of the Research

This study provides important insights into the potential of small-scale hydroelectric systems, however, there are some limitations to consider. First, the experiment was carried out in a controlled setting, which may not fully represent the real-life conditions in urban areas. Factors such as seasonal changes, unexpected weather events, and daily variations in energy use were

not fully simulated, which could affect how the system performs in real-world situations (Ugwu *et al.*, 2022; Oyinna *et al.*, 2023).

Second, the scale of the experiment was limited to a single hydroelectric setup. To get a better understanding of how these systems work in practice, future studies should consider testing multiple systems or integrating them with other renewable energy sources like solar or wind power. Finally, this study did not look into potential maintenance issues or the long-term durability of the system, which are important factors that could impact its efficiency over time (Muteba *et al.*, 2023).

5.3. Recommendation for Future Research

Future research should address the limitations identified in this study by pursuing a multi-faceted approach. One crucial area to explore is the long-term performance of small-scale hydroelectric systems in real-world urban environments. Conducting extended tests in diverse settings would provide a clearer picture of how these systems function over time. These studies should consider how factors like seasonal variations, unexpected weather events, and daily fluctuations in energy consumption influence the efficiency and reliability of the system. For instance, winter conditions might affect the availability of water and the system's ability to generate electricity, while summer heat could impact the performance of mechanical components. Understanding these dynamics is essential to adapting the system for optimal performance under varying conditions.

Another important area for future research is the integration of small-scale hydroelectric systems with other renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind power. This integration could create a more resilient and efficient energy grid for cities, where different sources complement each other. For example, solar panels might generate excess electricity during the day, which could then be used to pump water into storage reservoirs, while hydroelectric power

could be used during periods when solar or wind energy is less available. By creating a more interconnected and flexible energy system, cities could better manage supply and demand, reduce reliance on fossil fuels, and move closer to achieving sustainability goals.

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